

Thermodynamic Aspects of Complexation Reactions of some Transition Metal Ions with Diacetylmonoxime-thiosemicarbazone and Diacetylmonoxime-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone

P. P. HANKARE^a, R. S. RAMPURE^a, A. H. MANIKSHETE^a, L. P. DESHMUKH^a and C. K. BHASKARE^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shivaji University, P. G. Centre, Solapur-413 004

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur 416 001

Manuscript received 28 October 1991, revised 11 March 1992, accepted 19 March 1992

Diacetylmonoxime thiosemicarbazone is effective against vaccinia infections in mouse^{1,2} and probably acts by removing some essential metal ions from vaccinia virus chelation. In view of the importance of this ligand in chelation therapy, we report here complexation behaviour of diacetylmonoxime-thiosemicarbazone (DAMOTSC) and diacetylmonoxime-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (DAMOPTSC) with Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at temperatures 30, 40 and 50° (±0.1°) and at an ionic strength of 0.1 M employing Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique³ as applied by Irving and Rossotti⁴.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by using half integral and graphical methods⁴. The values of average stability constants are given in Table 1.

DAMOTSC and DAMOPTSC contain two dissociable protons one from oxime group and another from thiol group. These ligands undergo first deprotonation in the oxime and the second deprotonation in the thiol group. Mono-deprotonated species and di-deprotonated species are formed

successively in the first and second process of ionisations. Ligands are likely to be tridentate with oxygen, sulphur and nitrogen as active atoms.

From the titration data $\bar{n}_A$ values were calculated and plotted against corrected pH values to obtain pK values. Formation curve extends over a range of $\bar{n}_A$ values 0.1 to ≈ 1.9 and is wave-like. The pK₁^H and pK₂^H which correspond to the dissociation of protons from thiol and oxime groups were determined by half-integral method. The pK values were further corroborated by the linear plots of $\log (1 - \bar{n}_A)/\bar{n}_A$ vs pH and $\log (2 - \bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs pH. The pK values by both the methods are in agreement with each other.

Formation function n and pL were evaluated from the titration curves using standard expressions and n values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria. From the formation curves the values of stability constants ($\log K$) which correspond to 1:1 metal-ligand complex were determined. These values were further corroborated by plotting $\log (1 - \bar{n})/\bar{n}$ vs pL. The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complexa-

NOTES

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF BIVALENT METAL IONS WITH LIGANDS

Ligand	Cation	Stability constant	β at temp. °C			$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol		$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol		ΔS° (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		
			30°	40°	50°			30°	40°	50°		
DAMOTSC	H ⁺	log K_1^H	11.69	11.54	11.24	67.35	68.68	59.03	27.05	-133.01	-133.01	-129.98
	H ⁺	log K_1^H	10.02	9.91	9.78	57.73	58.98	60.07	19.84	-125.06	-125.06	-124.55
	Cu ²⁺	log K_1	9.48	9.36	9.17	54.62	55.71	56.32	21.64	-108.84	-108.84	-107.37
	Co ²⁺	log K_1	8.45	8.27	8.04	48.63	49.22	49.38	32.46	-53.55	-53.55	-52.38
	Ni ²⁺	log K_1	7.41	7.19	7.04	42.69	42.79	43.24	39.67	-9.96	-9.96	-11.04
	Zn ²⁺	log K_1	6.87	6.59	6.35	39.58	39.22	39.00	50.49	36.01	36.01	36.58
DAMOPTSC	Mn ²⁺	log K_1	6.35	6.02	5.66	36.59	35.83	34.76	59.51	75.66	75.66	76.62
	H ⁺	log K_1^H	11.80	11.59	11.41	67.99	68.98	70.08	37.97	-99.39	-99.39	-99.71
	H ⁺	log K_1^H	10.40	10.17	10.04	59.92	60.53	61.66	41.48	-60.87	-60.87	-62.50
	Cu ²⁺	log K_1	9.63	9.37	9.22	55.48	55.77	56.63	46.89	-28.37	-28.37	-30.16
	Co ²⁺	log K_1	8.45	8.23	7.96	48.63	48.98	48.89	39.67	-29.74	-29.74	-28.53
	Ni ²⁺	log K_1	7.65	7.37	7.11	44.08	43.86	43.67	50.49	21.18	21.18	21.13
Zn ²⁺	log K_1	6.95	6.78	6.92	40.04	40.35	40.66	30.66	30.98	30.98	30.97	
	Mn ²⁺	log K_1	6.49	6.21	5.80	37.39	36.96	35.62	50.49	43.24	43.24	46.04

tion have been determined using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs Helmholtz equation. Formation constant data and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1.

There are reports on the general trend of the stability constants by Calvin-Bjerrum techniques⁵⁻⁸. The order of stability constants in the above reports is as follows: Cu>Co>Ni⁵, Cu>Co>Ni>Mn>Zn>Cd⁶, Zn>Cu>Co>Ni>Mn⁷, Cu>Ni>Co>Zn>Mn⁸, and in the present work: Cu>Co>Ni>Zn>Mn; Irving-Williams rule⁹ is not strictly obeyed and Co and Ni show reverse order.

The stability constant decreases with an increase in temperature suggesting an exothermic nature of the interaction. The negative values of ΔG° indicate that the complexation reactions are spontaneous and the metal chelates are thermodynamically stable. Negative values of ΔH° indicate that the metal ligand bonds are fairly strong and complexation reactions are exothermic in nature. In the present work the negative ΔS° values were found in some metal-ligand complexes and in other systems positive values of ΔS° was observed which indicates favourable condition for chelate formation^{9,10}.

Relation between log K₁ and atomic numbers, ionisation potentials and electronegativities of metal ions: The log K₁ values of the metal-ligand systems were plotted against the atomic numbers of the metal ions. The plots showed a monotonic rise with a maximum at Cu followed by a fall and lower value of Mn¹¹. In the plots of log K₁ versus second ionisation potential of the metals, it is observed that stability increases from Mn to Cu and falls marginally with the fact that Zn is not a member of the first transition series¹². The plots of log K₁ versus electronegativities of the metals indicate that stability increases with increase in the electronegativity of the metals except Ni⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals except the chelating reagents were of A.R. grade. Details of the solutions and

experimental procedure used in the present study were the same as reported earlier¹³. Deionised carbonate-free water was used throughout. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solution (0.98 M) was prepared¹⁴. Solutions of the ligands were prepared in ethanol. Metal perchlorate solution were prepared by treating 2 M HClO₄ (20 ml) with excess of the oxide or carbonate of the metal (A.R.) and suitably diluting the resulting solutions to 100 ml of 0.2 M approximately. The metal contents were determined by standard procedures¹⁵.

Diacetylmonoxime (Merck, G.R.) was used as such. The thiosemicarbazone and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazone of diacetylmonoxime were prepared by refluxing diacetylmonoxime with thiosemicarbazide (AnalaR) and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (Fluka) respectively. For the synthesis of these ligands general procedure^{16,17} of condensation was used with certain modifications. The products were recrystallised from ethanol and their purities checked by tlc, m.p., ir and elemental analysis.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out using an Elico LI-120 pH meter with a Philips glass-calomel electrode assembly. The readings of pH meter were corrected for solvent effect as previously reported¹⁸. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere of oxygen-free nitrogen presaturated with solvent medium. Bubbling of nitrogen served the purpose of stirring. In order to determine the thermodynamic parameters the titrations were carried out at temperatures 30, 40 and 50° (±0.1°).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.S.R.) is thankful to Prof. N. N. Maldar for his keen interest, Prof. D. V. Jahagirdar for constant encouragement and Dr. U. R. Kapadi for his valuable suggestions and cooperation.

References

1. R. L. THOMPSON, J. DAVIS, P. B. RUSSELL and G. H. HITCHINGS, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Bio. Med.*, 1953, **84**, 496.

2. D. D. FERRIN, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1976, **64**, 181.
3. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase, Copenhagen, 1941.
4. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
5. Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH and R. S. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1214.
6. M. S. MAYADEV and M. V. KABADI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 850.
7. B. H. PATEL, J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 9.
8. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
9. D. R. GODDARD and S. I. NWANKWO, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1371.
10. G. DEGISCHER and G. R. CHOPPIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 2823.
11. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
12. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHOIR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
13. C. K. BHASKARE, P. P. HANKARE and R. S. RAMPURE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986 **63**, 286.
14. E. P. SERJEANT and A. ALBERT, "Determination of Ionisation Constants", 2nd ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1971.
15. A. I. VOGEL, "The Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1961.
16. A. V. ABLOV and N. I. BELICHUK, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **8**, 38.
17. J. M. C. PAVON, J. C. J. SANCHEZ and F. PINO, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1975, **75**, 335.
18. B. GUTBEZAHL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 565; R. G. BATES and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv Chim. Acta*, 1953, **38**, 699; R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 222.